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IMPACT OF INDIAN LOBBY ON PAK-US RELATIONS: ASSESSMENT OF COUNTERTERRORISM COOPERATION IN POST 9/11 ERA

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Abstract

The Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) collaborated with Pakistan's Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) to defeat the Soviet Union in Afghanistan. In the post-9/11 era, Indian foreign policymakers, intelligence operatives, and government officials are working on a single agenda to prove Pakistan uses proxies to bleed India. American officials under the Indian lobby's influence raised suspicions over Islamabad's role in overall counterterrorism operations. The post-Abbottabad operation era proved to be a menace as the Pakistani state is continuously viewed with suspicion for providing safe havens to key Al Qaeda members. The ISI's sacrifices to kill, capture, and extradite Al Qaeda operatives in collaboration with CIA counterterrorism teams are viewed with suspicion. In short, the Indian lobby in the US has achieved the Indian objective to de-hyphenate Pakistan from the US and suspend military assistance and equipment. Qualitative methods helped authors acquire and analyze data in pursuit of accessing Indian statecraft's use of the Indian lobby in America. This academic paper aims to gain a deep understanding of Indian foreign policy objectives i.e., to isolate Islamabad in the international community, suspend American financial assistance, stop the supply of advanced American weapons to Pakistan, halt economic aid and, if possible, declare Pakistan as a state sponsoring terrorism.

Keywords: CIA, Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI), Counterterrorism, Indian Lobby

Introduction

The aim of this academic inquiry is to examine Pakistan's cooperation with America in the War on Terror (WOT). It highlights Pakistan's substantial counterterrorism measures to completely root out Al Qaeda. Yet, the services and sacrifices rendered by Pakistan could not get recognition from America. The paper highlights two contrary diplomatic approaches adopted by India and Pakistan in pursuit of achieving their national security and foreign policy objectives. Indian foreign office was able to set national objectives, foreign policy goals, and priorities.

The highest professional standards and the long-term strategic investment enabled the Indian foreign office to follow the Indian lobby in America. Contrary to Indian professionalism and the highest standards Pakistan's foreign office and various governments adopted stagnant approaches, they rejected innovation, turned a blind eye to developments on international forums, and denied retrospect of its foreign policy goals and national interest.

Pre 9/11, Era Policy

In the 1980s, the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) waged a propaganda war against the Soviet forces in Afghanistan. The CIA collaborated with Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) to radicalize, train and equip Arabs. Later, India alleged that Pakistan is promoting regional instability through radical ideology, exporting terrorism as a state policy. The Research and Analysis Wing (RAW) covert/overt operators and clandestine analysts focused their energies on Pakistan. First, waging information warfare, second, narrative building, third, countering Pakistan's proxies and launching clandestine operations against Pakistan to settle the score, and; finally, Pakistan-specific policy remained static. India is isolating Islamabad regionally and portraying Pakistan as a reckless terror-sponsoring state for its use of irregular warfare in Kashmir (Levy & Scott-Clark, 2021).

India launched information warfare. They first, alleged Pakistan for sponsoring the Sikh insurgent movement and the insurgency in the Indian Occupied Kashmir (IOK). The Pashtun tribesmen's 1947-48, military operation to liberate Kashmir and hosting Arab Mujahideen fighting the Soviets was presented as evidence to convince America, of Islamabad's proxies. Naturally, India projected itself as a victim of Pakistan-sponsored terrorism. Secondly, to convince America that India is employing a policy of restraint vis-à-vis Pakistan's use of proxies. However, Adrian Levy believes the Indian security agency remained a low profile and sponsored proxies across Pakistan. RAW operative and analyst Rahman proposed the idea of equivalence to burn Karachi, Lahore, and Baluchistan to give a befitting response to Pakistan's proxies. Consequently, RAW raised assassination units, sponsored target killings in Karachi, and financed and fueled the Balochistan insurgency, it exploited ethnic fault lines, and sectarian violence to burn Pakistan (Levy & Scott-Clark, 2021).

Literature Review

This section highlights India is using authors, journalists, academicians, analysts, CIA analysts, and American lawmakers to propagate the Indian stance before large-scale audiences and various committees of the US Executive Branch including the Subcommittee on Terrorism, Non-Proliferation, and Trade, Subcommittee on Asia and the Pacific, Committee on Foreign Affairs House of Representatives (Pakistan Friend Or, 2016), House Homeland Security Committee (Tankel, 2013) to prove Pakistan is a terror-sponsoring state. Notable missionaries include C. Christine Fair and Sumit Ganguly (Fair & Ganguly, 2015), Nicholas Schmidle, Lisa Curtis, and Hussain Haqqani (Curtis, 2017), Bruce Riedel (Riedel, 2018), Vanda Felbab-Brown (Felbab-Brown, 2018), Sahar Khan (Khan, 2018), Kay Johnson and Drazen Jorgic, Kirishnadey Calamur (Calamur, 2018), Stephen Tankel (Tankel, Storming the World, 2013), Zachary

Cansantino, Assistant Professor at American University Dr. Tricia Bacon, and Long War Journal's Senior Editor Bill Roggio. Pro-Indian US Lawmakers include Matt Salmon, Chairman of the Subcommittee on Asia and the Pacific, William Keating, Ted Poe, Dana Rohrabacher, the architect of the myth Peshawar Shura Ambassador Zalmay Khalilzad, Diane Feinstein, and Bob Corker.

Funding foreign authors and creating an "Indian Chair" in American think tanks is New Delhi's long-term strategy to tarnish Pakistan's image. Reports written in these think tanks e.g., The Center for American Progress (Wadhams, 2007), Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) (Hong Niao Series, 2021), United States Institute of Peace (Constantino, 2020), POGO, RAND Corporation (Hanauer & Chalk, 2012), Middle East Review of International Affairs (Rubin, 2002), Brookings (Kalb, 2021), Observer Research Foundation (ORF) (Kaura, 2017), and Carnegie Endowment for Peace (Tellis, 2019) focus on Afghanistan, India, Pakistan and terrorism in South Asia echoes, ISI supports LeT, terrorism in IOK, Afghan Taliban, and the Haqani Network fighting against the US and allied forces. Content includes Pakistani tribal areas that have remained safe havens for terrorists. The myth of Quetta Shura was created after the killing of Afghan Taliban head Mullah Akhtar Mansour in the Naushki area on May 21, 2016 (Rasmussen & Boone, 2016). Former Pentagon official Michael Rubin, for instance, deliberately twisted facts and ground realities by linking Faisal Shahzad, the perpetrator of the foiled Times Square bombing, to Jaish-e-Mohammed (JEM) and Pakistan's ISI (Time To Declare, 2017). Contrary to Rubin's on-purpose allegations, the US Department of Justice has acknowledged that TTP slain chief Hakim Ullah Mahsud claimed responsibility for the foiled attack on Times Square (Pakistani Taliban Leader, 2010). Shahzad was trained by Tehreek-Taliban Pakistan (TTP) declared a defunct terrorist organization by the US and

Pakistan. TTP is involved in attacks on Pakistani civilians, school children the armed forces, the ISI, government buildings, and assassinated politicians like Benazir Bhutto.

Indian Lobby: Impact on Pakistan's Counterterrorism Operations

In reaction to the 9/11 terrorist attacks, America attacked Afghanistan on October 7, 2001, to topple the Taliban regime for sheltering Oussama-Bin-Laden (OBL) (Thompson, 2021). Indian intelligence officers tried to convince the Bush Administration that Pakistan sponsored Al Qaeda to launch the 9/11 terrorist attacks. Fortunately, US intelligence could not find any linkages. CIA special counterterrorist operatives enjoyed the autonomy to operate freely across Pakistan's urban areas. Ramzi Bin Al Shibhi, coordinator of the 9/11, attacks was arrested by CIA's Special Activities Division and ISI in a joint operation conducted in Karachi on September 11, 2002 (Ramzi Bin Al-Shibh, n.d.). Al Qaeda's financier and planner of the 9/11 attacks Abu Zubaydah was arrested by the CIA team led by John Kiriakou Chief of Counterterrorism Operations in Pakistan and Pakistani security agencies in Faisalabad (Worth, 2022) in a joint operation. George Bush branded Abu Zubaydah as one of Al Qaeda's "top operatives" (Leopold, 2013). Kiriakou later revealed CIA and Pakistani security agencies raided a dozen suspected locations on a single night to arrest Abu Zubaydah involving over three dozen CIA counterterrorist operatives (Kiriakou). In March 2003, Khalid Sheikh Muhammad (KSM) the brain of Al Qaeda and architect of the 9/11 attacks was arrested by Pakistan's ISI in Rawalpindi. Al Qaeda's Operational Chief Abu Faraj Al-Libbi was arrested in May 2005. Al Libi planned and supervised an assassination attempt against Pervez Musharraf. In 2010, CIA Station Chief Jonathan Bank's replacement with Mark Kelton proved the Pakistani state was aware of the presence of top spy officials in Pakistan.

India persistently lobbied against Pakistan in the US to prove ISI and Pakistan military are harboring terrorists to destabilize the region by killing American and ally forces in Afghanistan. India was able to sow seeds of suspicions and fracture Pakistan's credibility as an ally. The US kept the Pakistani security, political, and intelligence community uninformed and carried covert operation to kill OBL near Pakistan Military Academy (PMA) Abbottabad. It strengthened the Indian narrative causing irreversible damage, a trust deficit, and dividing American government officials into pro and anti-Pakistan quarters. In the post-OBL era, Pakistani security agencies' previous efforts to kill or arrest the highest-ranking Al Qaeda members were questioned. A month later member of the House Foreign Affairs Committee Dan Burton told US intelligence reports that several quarters in Pakistan protected bin, Laden. CIA Deputy Director Michael Morell ranked Pakistani assistance in counterterrorism as 3 on a scale of 1 to 10. Indian outcry that Pakistan was playing a double game by supporting Al Qaeda and Afghan Taliban gained US lawmakers' acknowledgment. On June 14, 2011, the Head of the House Intelligence Committee Mike Rogers, alleged that officials of the ISI and Pakistan's army had helped protect bin Laden, (Pakistan Arrests Informants, 2011). Either Pakistan ignored US lawmakers' suspicions or it was unaware of these reports. Contrary to US allegations, pressure tactics, coercive diplomacy, condemnation, suspicions, suspension of military aid, bigotry, treachery, and deceit Islamabad continued counterterrorism cooperation with Washington. Pakistani intelligence agencies continued intelligence sharing and conducted joint counterterrorism operations with the CIA.

In May 2011, the leader of Arab Afghans in Afghanistan Muhammad Ali Qasim Yaqub alias Abu Shoaib al Makki was arrested in Karachi (Senior al Qaeda, 2011). On August 22, 2011,

Atiya Abdul Rehman was eliminated in a drone attack in the Waziristan region. On June 3, 2011, Ilyas Kashmiri was killed in a drone attack on a tip-off information. Kashmiri leader of Harkat-ul-Jihad Islami (HUJI) was on the State Department's "specially designated global terrorist." (Georgy & Anthony, 2011). Umar Farooq Al Qaeda Operational Chief for Pakistan and Afghanistan was killed in Datta Khel North Waziristan (Sherazi & Yan, 2014). Younas al Mauritani, personally tasked by OBL to attack economic interests in the US, Europe, and Australia was arrested in Quetta in an ISI-CIA coordinated operation (Imtiaz & Yousaf, 2011). The Washington Post claimed Mauritani was planning to launch attacks against "American water reservoirs, oil and gas pipelines, American ships and oil tankers using explosive-laden speed boats," (Brulliard, 2011). CIA hunted Al Qaeda's top leaders on Pakistani soil, in the largest counterterrorism operations in the world to extradite, dislocate to Al Qaeda's command and control (C2), kill, or capture them with impunity across Pakistan attests to ISI's sincerity in fighting WOT. Michael Leiter, Director of the U.S. National Counterterrorism Center (Sanger & Mazzetti, 2010) acknowledged CIA's drone strikes targeting Al Qaeda in Pakistani tribal areas (Ahmed, Khan, & Fayaz, 2022) that led to the killings of innocent civilians including men, women, children and the elderly. It caused large-scale hatred for Pakistani security agencies, anti-Americanism, the rise of terrorist groups, and incidents of terrorism across Pakistan.

Instead of acknowledging ISI, military, and Pakistani state efforts e.g., loss of security personnel, serving Generals, civilian casualties, loss of reputation globally, and huge economic losses Bush's successors doubted and started questioning Pakistan's counterterrorism struggles. Letitia Tish Long, Director National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency highlighted Khalid Sheikh Mohammad and Abu Faraj Al-Libbi's presence and arrests from settled areas

of Rawalpindi and Mardan, Pakistan (Graff, 2021). Point-fingering and critique of Pakistani security agencies manifest deep distrust and American suspicions. The Trump administration's close working relationship with Modi's administration enabled India to further widen the gulf, tear apart counterterrorism coordination, and deepen mistrust and suspicions regarding Pakistan's counterterrorism efforts. President Trump and National Security Adviser H.R. McMaster (Schmidle, 2018) adopted a hardline suspending Pakistan's military assistance. Trump, an admirer of India, adopted a tougher stance by lobbying with members of the Financial Action Task Force (FATF) to put Pakistan's name on the gray list (Johnson & Jorgic, 2018) Indian lobby is representing Pakistan's metropolitans as terrorists' safe-havens. The country's telecommunication sector, transportation system, and financial network are portrayed as helping hands enabling terrorists to have international outreach.

Instability in Afghanistan

Indian policy towards Pakistan and jargon i.e., Quetta Shura, Pakistan as a terrorist state, terror-sponsoring state, or haven for terrorism in Pakistan remain unchanged. Prime Minister Manmohan Singh's administration including Minister for External Affairs late Pranab Mukherjee, S.M. Krishna, and Salman Khurshid alleged Pakistan for instability in Afghanistan. Indian selection of jargon and its strategic use permeated American lawmakers. Senator John F. Kerry on December 9, 2009, regarded Pakistan as a "core... challenge," in Afghanistan. Kerry echoed Lashkar-e-Tayyiba's (LeT) presence in Afghanistan (The New Afghanistan, 2009). Interestingly, the LeT has neither threatened American citizens nor been involved in attacks against American interests. Likewise, Senator Richard G. Lugar questioned whether Pakistan would work with America to eradicate OBL and major al-Qaeda leaders.

Modi administration's Minister for External Affairs i.e., the late Sushma Swaraj and Dr. S. J. Shankar continued propaganda against Pakistan. The Indian narrative was accepted by then-President Trump. In 2017, Trump alleged that "Pakistan often gives haven to agents of chaos, violence, and terror... We can no longer be silent about Pakistan's safe havens for terrorist organizations, the Taliban, and other groups that pose a threat to the region and beyond," (Remarks by President, 2017). The main purpose of holding Pakistan responsible for the chaos in Afghanistan in the eyes of the US was to increase the Indian foothold in the war-torn country. India established its consulate in Jalalabad near Malakand, Tor-Kham, Landi Kotal, and Parachinar. India chose strategically located Kandahar borders Pakistan's Chaman, and Pishin, and the area is close to Quetta, Khost, Mastung, and Naushki. The Indian intelligence created webs of terrorist networks to destabilize Baluchistan and tribal areas of Pakistan (Jamal, 2020).

Waging Propaganda Warfare

The Indian government is spending billions to operate bogus websites, fake media outlets, and online newspapers in different languages particularly in e.g., English, French, German, Arabic, and Russian to represent Pakistan as a state-sponsoring terrorism, a renegade state. A worldwide web operated by a hostile intelligence agency was discovered by EU Lab (Jaaved, 2022). Indian Foreign Office alleges Pakistan is a sponsor of terrorism or epicenter of terrorism at the highest forums (India Slams Pak, 2020). India is using foreign journalists, and authors working in world-leading news agencies to promote New Delhi's decades-old narrative that Pakistan harbored terrorism and was responsible for American failure, killing American and allied forces in Afghanistan through its proxies, Haqqani Network, Al Qaeda, and Afghan Taliban.

New Delhi achieved its desired objectives e.g., the suspension of US military, technical,

and financial assistance to Pakistan through a well-structured and coordinated strategy to isolate Islamabad. Pakistan has lost significance in Washington, repeatedly resolutions have been tabled in US Congress to declare Pakistan as a terrorist state, and allegations that Pakistan's security apparatus is a source of regional instability. Contrarily, neither Pakistani authorities, institutions, think tanks or academicians have ever tried to counter Indian policy. Indian gains at the expense of Pakistan's losses are pointless for Islamabad's based policymakers. Dead Horses' occupying Pakistan's decision-making nerve center needs to alter their approach to at least preserve Pakistan's interests and stop Indian endless point-scoring.

India is a Victim of Pakistan State-Sponsored Terrorism

Numerous US government officials, lawmakers, authors, journalists, and academicians are successfully convinced by Indian government officials that Pakistan's state policy is to sponsor terrorism and New Delhi is a victim of Pakistan-sponsored terrorism. Indian assets are provided access to prestigious Committees of the American Senate. C. Christine Fair while briefing the US Committee on Foreign Relations on May 24, 2011, pushed the Indian narrative to convince the Committee that the LeT bleeds India with Pakistan's support. Fair sincerity to the Indian cause is undeniable as she broadened LeT's support base including the Pakistani state, diaspora, and ordinary Pakistani citizens (Bergen, Fair, Kerry, Lugar, & Pillar, 2011). American military leadership is not immune from this narrative, for instance, General David Petraeus Commander of U.S. Central Command while briefing the US Senate's Committee on Foreign Relations, on Afghanistan out of the blue brought into discussion the LeT and Mumbai attacks. During President Obama's administration Indian lobby endeavored to prove the LeT is emerging as a global terrorist syndicate and a long-term

threat to the US and its European allies. The United Nations (UN) website associates the LeT Chief Hafiz Muhammad Saeed with Palestinian scholar, theologian, and OBL's mentor Abdullah Azzam (Hafiz Muhammad Saeed, 2009), founder of Maktab al-Khidmat. Al Qaeda was founded after the assassination of Azzam to replace al-Khidmat and its cause to liberate Palestine. LeT is also associated with the Taliban. US policymakers working as an Indian lobby deliberately conceal facts that LeT follows Salafi ideology contrary to the Taliban's Deo-Bandi Philosophy. Al Qaeda leadership believes the LeT supports the Pakistani establishment therefore the group is misled. Consequently, Taliban-LeT's and Al Qaeda-LeT's differing ideologies and perceptions prevent them from cooperating. Yet, American senators and top-ranking officials (referred to as Indian lobby) i.e., former Deputy Secretary of State and Deputy Assistant Secretary of Defense for East Asia and Pacific Affairs Richard Armitage (Richard L. Armitage, n.d.), Assistant to the President for National Security Affairs Samuel R. Berger, South Asia portfolio on the Secretary's Policy Planning Staff at the U.S. Department of State Daniel S. Markey (Markey, n.d.) related the LeT with Al Qaeda and regarded it as a branch of Taliban (Armitage, Berger, & Markey, 2010). Indian lobbyists on purpose inaccurately associate the LeT with Al Qaeda, the Afghan Taliban, and particularly with Pakistani security apparatus to declare Pakistan as a threat to regional stability hence a terror-sponsoring state. In 2011, the US Federal Prosecutor linked the LeT with the Pakistani secret service and inducted both in the Mumbai attacks (Rotella, 2018). In 2012, the Obama administration pressured Pakistan by designating the LeT as a terrorist group (Rotella, U.S. Government Pressures, 2012). In September 2016 Senator Ted Poe and Rohrabacher presented a bill HR 6069 or the Pakistan State Sponsor of Terrorism Act (US Lawmakers Move, 2016). India was

lobbying tirelessly to convince serving and former US lawmakers to designate Pakistan state sponsoring terrorism e.g., architect of the Pressler Amendment Former Republican Senator Larry Pressler strongly urged the US government "to declare Pakistan a terrorist state," ([US Must Declare, 2017](#)).

In 2018, the Trump administration commemorated the completion of the 10th anniversary of the Mumbai attacks. US Secretary of State Mike Pompeo asked "Pakistan to... implement sanctions against... LeT and its affiliates," ([US to Pakistan, 2018](#)). During the Balakot crisis John Bolton, the then US National Security Advisor offered US assistance and backed the Indian attack inside Pakistan's settled area. Bolton stated that "America supports India's right to self-defense." US Secretary of State Mike Pompeo tweeted "We stand with #India as it confronts terrorism. Pakistan must not provide safe havens for terrorists to threaten international security." White House Press Secretary Sarah Sanders told Islamabad to instantly terminate its backing to all terrorist syndicates and not to provide safe havens ([We Support India's, 2019](#)). Congressman Perry presented a bill alleging Pakistan for sponsoring the Pulwama attack. Lawmakers demanded that Pakistan eliminate terrorists' safe havens of Jaish-e-Muhammad ([Perry Demands Pakistani, 2019](#)). Bolton recently hinted that the US provided intelligence information to India regarding targets in Balakot ([Former American NSA, 2020](#)). On January 27, 2022, US Senator Scott Perry urged President Joe Biden to scrap the appointment of Masood Khan as Islamabad's envoy to Washington. Perry labeled Khan as a sympathizer and praiser of Hizbul Mujahideen and Burhan Wani ([US Congressman Urges, 2022](#)). Later in March 2022 Perry presented a bill in the House of Representatives and forwarded it to the Committee on Foreign Affairs to label Pakistan as a State Sponsor of Terrorism ([Bill Tabled in, 2022](#)). India started lobbying against Khan's appointment because

of his expertise on the Kashmir issue. Pakistan Foreign Ministry's Spokesperson Asim Iftikhar Ahmad termed it a slice of the broader Indian propaganda operation to malign Pakistan and individuals who represent it, by using sham news to make disgraceful claims and groundless allegations ([FO Refutes Indian, 2022](#)).

Creating Hurdles in the Supply of US Military Equipment

In 1998, Senator Rohrabacher leveled allegations against Pakistan for transferring unexploded Tomahawk missiles fired at OBL's hideout in Afghanistan to the People's Republic of China (PRC). In May 2011 US lawmakers ([Rogin, 2011](#)) reiterated allegations stating that Pakistan may have authorized PRC to access proprietary technologies used in American military helicopter crashes during Operation Geronimo ([Bin Laden Raid, 2011](#)). Z-20, manufactured by PRC's Helicopter Research and Development Institute, is allegedly reverse engineering the American Stealth Black Hawk left behind by the American seals on May 2, 2011. India pushes its lobby to repeatedly highlight these issues. A report published by CSIS in 2021 claims that PRC's Hong Niao HN-Missile series is reversed engineering of the US Tomahawk cruise missiles ([How Pakistan Gave, 2021](#)). In March 2016 India openly lobbied against the approval of eight F-16s fighter aircraft and radar sales to Pakistan. US Senators Rand Paul, Bob Corker Chairman Senate Foreign Relations Committee, and John McCain, Indian-American Democrat Ami Bera ([US to Go, 2016](#)) were able to make a coalition of another 20 senators and presented a resolution against fighter aircraft sale in the Senate ([Bagchi, 2016](#)). Countered resolution manifests the Indian agency's growing influence and the ability to mend the minds of US senators.

Suspension of Military Aid

The RAW continuous efforts using the platform of the Indian government, foreign authors, Indian Chairs at various think tanks,

and news reports assured US President Barack Obama and President Trump that Pakistan is diverting military aid, providing weapons, training, and intelligence information to support terrorists in attacking US and NATO forces. In May 2009, the Indian lobby in collaboration with officials from the Pentagon, the State Department, the House of Representatives, and the Senate asked the Obama administration to set a benchmark for Pakistan to gauge Islamabad's commitment to the fight against Al Qaeda, Haqqani Network and Afghan Taliban ([Obama Preparing Benchmarks, 2009](#)). In October 2009 Congressman Frank Wolf snapped at Senator Zafar Ali Shah while he was complaining about the provision of conditional aid to Pakistan ([Rajghatta, 2009](#)). In July 2011 Pak-US bilateral relations worsened to an extent that top officials in the Obama administration including William Daley, President Chief of Staff, and Hillary Clinton US Secretary of State confirmed the suspension of US \$ 800 million in aid to Pakistan were suspended ([US Suspends \\$800m, 2011](#)). The Indian intelligence network made a breakthrough in May 2012 when Dona Rohrabacher, Diane Feinstein, and Bob Corker questioned Islamabad's allegiance to the US and introduced a bill to stop aid to Pakistan ([Rajghatta, More Pressure on Obama to Stop Aid to Pak, 2011](#)). Congressional assets are obliged in the form of visits to India and to different parts of the world e.g., Rohrabacher was invited as a key speaker to address a session in London over the issue of holding a referendum in Balochistan ([US Congressman Rohrabacher, 2013](#)). Contrarily, Rohrabacher did not condemn human rights violations nor demanded holding a referendum on IOK in the light of United Nations Security Council Resolutions (UNSCRs). US Congressman has kept silent over Indian murderous government human rights violations in Kashmir Rohrabacher's words murderous government even after the discovery of mass graves in 2009. The key takeaway gleaned from

Rohrabacher's demand for holding a referendum in Baluchistan and silence over the Kashmir issue is perhaps he is receiving financial assistance from the Intelligence Bureau (IB) and RAW. Canada's Global News reported that IB and RAW have been using money since 2009 to influence Canadian politicians. The prime motive of the operation was to assure lawmakers that Islamabad was using Canadian funding for sponsoring terrorism ([Ahmad, 2020](#)). Rohrabacher and Bera both were rewarded by scheduling their visit to India in February 2017 ([27 US Lawmakers, 2017](#)) and October 2017 ([US Congressional Delegation, 2017](#)) as a part of US delegations. Indian lobbying success can be measured by the poisoning of Pak-US relations and the reduction of military aid from \$ 1.6 billion in 2003 to \$ 319.7 million in the fiscal year 2017.

In January 2018 Trump suspended military aid worth \$ 900 million to Pakistan's Foreign Military Financing (FMF). It endowed Pakistan to purchase U.S. military hardware, train military officials in the US, and other services. The second category of aid was provided to reimburse Islamabad's financial cost spent in fighting WOT under the Coalition Support Fund (CSF). Both the FMF and the CSF were suspended for not carrying out kinetic operations against the Haqqani Network and Afghan Taliban. US State Department officials justify the decision as launching pads from Pakistan resulted in the killings of Afghan, US, and allied forces ([Mohammed & Landay, 2018](#)). Washington viewed it as a punitive measure e.g., suspension of military assistance to Pakistan. It was a huge victory for India as Islamabad despite military casualties, civilian deaths, economic losses, and political uncertainty created by a wave of terror was declared an untrustworthy ally.

On September 11 and 15, 2022 Indian Defence Minister Rajnath Singh registered protests to US Secretary of Defense Lloyd Austin over \$ 450 Million in sustenance aid for

Pakistan's aging F-16s. Earlier India criticized the US decision to provide sustenance assistance to Pakistan during two plus two inter-sessional meetings with Donald Lu.

Conclusion

The study highlights Indian foreign policy is to, consistently lobby in pursuit of maximizing its gains. Indian diplomats are making these gains at the cost of Pakistan's interests. Perpetual security completion with Pakistan requires New Delhi either to compromise its foreign policy objectives and national interests or undermine Islamabad's significance and isolate Pakistan.

The subtle foreign policy objectives isolated Islamabad particularly in America, at the regional level in the Islamic world and international forums. Lack of interest to protect, preserve, or promote the national interest, substantial negligence and the Pakistani elite's decision to subordinate foreign policy objectives/national interests to their gains are among other reasons ensuring Indian success. The worst outcome can be the American decision to designate Pakistan as an American enemy and terror-sponsoring state. Islamabad will have to introduce systemic changes in pursuit of a common set of foreign policy goals and identify and neutralize immediate/tactical problems and long-term strategic threats.

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